

FORMATION OF EARTH ETHICS IN THE CONTEXT OF TECHNOLOGICAL CULTURE OF THE LATE MODERN ERA

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ABSTRACT

Object of research: technological culture as a matrix of interaction of the components of the system “man – society – nature/Earth”.

Investigated problem: the substantiation of the meaning of the Ethics of the Earth in the context of technological culture, transforms the moral and value system of the late Modern era and provokes the emergence of the era of Posthumanism.

The main scientific results: the definition of the technological culture of the late Modern era made it possible to determine the existing contradictions in the moral dimension of the existence of man and the Earth. It should be noted that in the context of the technological transformation of the Earth, the existing ethics as a monoparadigm of the Enlightenment does not correspond to the challenges of the beginning of the XXI century. It is emphasized that the ethical dimension of the introduction of technologies into the existence of the Earth is an indispensable component of modern scientific discourse. It is not only about the ethical dimension of technology, but also the importance of the formation of the Ethics of the Earth. This allows to conclude that a person determines its moral position relative to the Earth in the context of the technological transformation of the Earth's existence.

The scope of practical use of the research results: the research results can be used in teaching such normative courses as “Philosophy”, “Philosophical Anthropology”, “Culturology” for students and undergraduates, graduate students of humanitarian and technical faculties.

Innovative technological product: Ethics of the Earth destroys the concept of the Earth as an object that is external to humans. The anthropological dimension of the Earth testifies to the fact that a person should be clearly aware of the responsibility for its activities, since the existence of the Earth is a condition for the existence of a person.

The scope of using the innovative technological product: the substantiation of the Earth Ethics corresponds to the polyparadigmatic optics of the modern post-non-classical scientific discourse, where a person is one of the constituent parts of the nature/Earth system. The post-non-classical paradigm eliminates the New European anthropocentrism, striking the consequences of which the person of the late Modern era feels. We are talking about environmental and anthropological crises that occur in the space of the Earth in the coordinates of technological culture.

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1. Introduction

1.1. The object of research

The object of research is technological culture as a matrix of interaction of the components of the system “man – society – nature/Earth”.

1.2. Problem description

Technological culture as one of the modes of transformation of modern culture is associated with the rapid development of technologies of the late XX – early XXI centuries, causing a new paradigmatic shift [1]. One of the pressing problems of modern scientific-natural and social-humanitarian discourse is the problem of rethinking the relationship of man to the Earth, in connection with the spread of innovative technologies (nanotechnology, molecular biological technologies, virtual reality technologies, etc.). The latter, firstly, testify to the formation of a new ontological

paradigm of all living things, and secondly, they make one think about the possible consequences of unlimited knowledge. Ukrainian philosopher Myroslav Popovych at the end of the XX century substantiated the principle of “being human”, which in the first decades of the XXI century requires clarification: “to be human on Earth”, which is associated with the articulation of the idea of the nearest cybernetic future (K. Hales).

1. 3. Suggested solution to the problem.

Technological culture, as a project of a technological civilization, gradually displaces both man and nature/Earth, touching upon such a phenomenon as body/corporeality, despite the fact that the connection between the Earth’s body and the human body is eternal, as evidenced by the history of the formation of mankind. The eternity of this connection is emphasized by the studies of philosophers of the late Modern era. Thus, M. Merleau-Ponty [2] introduces the concept of “flesh of the world flesh” into the scientific dictionary, which brings researchers back to the problem of the relationship between man and the Earth in order to find a fulcrum for their own existence. According to J. Deleuze and F. Quattari, human activity is a kind of tattoo of the body of the Earth. So, the activity of society is to “stuff tattoos, cut, separate, mutilate, scar, make incisions, initiate” [3]. S. Alaimo emphasizes that corporeality is a hostage of the future and will obviously require “correction” in the near future [4]. Ukrainian philosopher L. Gazniuk notes: “Man in its somatic being does not stand in opposition to nature ... By inflicting wounds on nature, the body of the Earth, a person thereby inflicts wounds on itself, and therefore in the age of the rapid development of civilization it is necessary to see not “another self”, and a part of oneself – in the unfolding of nature” [5]. This allows to say that the anthropocentric paradigm of the late Modernity in the context of technological culture acquires a new configuration, allows philosophers to attract such markers as transhumanism, posthumanism, and the like. Questions of improving both man and nature/Earth arise, articulating the problem of the formation of the Ethics of the Earth. The well-known photographs of the Earth “Blue Marble” and “East of the Earth”, which have acquired a symbolic meaning of the beauty and vulnerability of the Earth in the plane of technological culture, appear as emblems of the Earth, are now subject to man.

2. Materials and methods

The problem of the formation of ethics in the context of the technological civilization of the late Modern era is due to the processes of cultural transformation. First of all, we are talking about the formation of a technological culture, which has a significant impact on the interaction of social communities in a technological civilization. K. Dawson emphasizes that technological culture “is a huge complex of techniques and areas of specialization without a spirit that directs without a basis for common moral values, without a cohesive spiritual goal. Culture of this kind is not at all a culture in the traditional sense, that is, not in an order that would contain each side of human life in a spiritual community” [6]. According to the researcher, technological culture appears to be a source of personality disorientation, since it is technologies that determine the specifics of a person’s being, as a result of which traditional markers of understanding as a person are destroyed/society and the Earth. A person finds itself in a situation where moral values not only arise fluid, which corresponds to “flowing modernity” (S. Bauman), but are also constructed by technological culture. This situation articulates the problem of technologization of the objective reality of future humanity as a post-humanity, what takes on a contradictory character. So, changes in the methodological optics of philosophical knowledge at the end of the XX century associated with the search for a new humanism, is a kind of response to the processes of technologization.

The theoretical and methodological foundations of the study of the Ethics of the Earth in the context of technological culture are based on an interdisciplinary synthesis and a cultural-anthropological approach to determine the changes that the concept of humanism and traditional markers “good”/“evil” are undergoing. Such research methods are applied as phenomenological (for analyzing the co-existence of man and the Earth as subject-subject relations), hermeneutic (for analyzing the essence of the Earth in the context of the narratives of technological culture, for example, technohumanism, posthumanism, transhumanism), comparative civilization).

So technohumanism acts as a new look at the co-existence of the Earth and man, changing the basic existentials of their existence: “Like all humanistic sects, technohumanism makes human will too sacred, seeing in it the nail on which the entire Universe hangs. Technogumanism expects

our desires to choose which mental abilities to develop and thereby determine the shape of the future mind. But what will happen when technological progress allows reforming and designing these very desires? “[7]. Technohumanism not only testifies to the radical transformation of humanism, it also focuses on the human figure, its new possibilities: the figure of the “master of planet Earth” begins to expand to the horizons of the figure “master of the galaxy”. A feature of transhumanism, as opposed to technohumanism, is the confidence in overcoming the natural limitations of a person as a mortal being, that is, confidence in the immutability of human nature. The latter arises as a subject and an object, opens up new possibilities for the emergence of a superman figure. So, H. Arendt in the 60s of the XX century defined this situation as a human condition, remained alone with itself and confronts itself exclusively [8].

We are talking about a post-anthropological turn, which is marked by the rejection of values, including humanistic ones, which provokes the formation of a new system of coordinates – post-humanistic. According to S. Alaimo, the subject’s attitude to the environment (not a person at all) depends more on its assessment of the technologies used in the interaction process [9]. Note: if the concept of transhumanism is widely used, then the concept of technohumanism is just beginning to bother researchers. Unlike transhumanism, which is understood as a marker of possible transformations of human corporeality as a result of the use of technology, marks the characteristics of the posthuman era or the era of rejection of man in its classical sense, technohumanism is understood as a “successful version” of modern European humanism (Yu. N. Harari) [7]. Despite the fact that opinions are expressed that humanity is now experiencing the last version of itself [10], the problem of the environment remains without attention, despite the use of such markers as “posthumanism”, “transhumanism”, “technohumanism”, “post-humanism”, “technological man” and others.

A new era of the Enlightenment is emerging, but the Technological Enlightenment, which represents a metaphor for human substitution, where technologization embodies an instrumental disjunction: if you want to know, you have to do [11]. Man translates these ideas to nature/Earth; a person is faced with a choice: to dissolve in the technological world or to abandon the temptation that the existence of technology provides to it.

3. Research results and their discussion

Environmental risks of the beginning of the XXI century articulated the problem of the co-existence of man and the Earth in the context of the paradigm of ethics, which is undergoing significant transformations and can be designated as the situation of the centaur problem due to the elimination of the distinction between biological and technological, natural and artificial. A new historical situation arises, conditioned by technological, ecological and anthropological factors, changing the usual markers of existence. The main thing is recognized as the formation of a polyparadigmatic scientific discourse, where the main place is occupied by the complementary connection between the natural and humanitarian sciences. The reality of the Earth is presented in combination with human existence, in the plane of social and technological meanings of human existence.

Disappointing forecasts of the possible consequences of technology were articulated by J. Baudrillard, J. Deleuze, F. Fukuyama and other philosophers of the twentieth century. Thus, according to F. Fukuyama, society is able to exercise effective control over biotechnology, which makes it impossible to exclusively optimistic prospects for the development of mankind [12]. K. Hales refers to the changes that occur in relation to living things. The researcher gives the following example: “At the Fourth Conference on Artificial Life in the summer of 1994, evolutionary biologist Thomas S. Ray made two proposals. The first concerned the Costa Rican rainforest biodiversity conservation plan. The second proposal was that the Tierra program, which creates forms of artificial life in computers, be brought online so that it could “display” different species on computers around the world. Ray believed these proposals were complementary. The first was aimed at enhancing biological diversity for proteinaceous life forms; the second sought the same for “silicon” life forms. Their neighborhood dramatically illustrates the restructuring of nature that is taking place in the field of artificial life, which is affectionately called “AL” (from artificial life). [This attitude is striking] ... the computer codes that make up such “creatures” become a natural form of life, and only the environment is artificial” [13].

In this regard, one should turn to the problem of ethics in the context of the reflections of G. Jonas, who, with the help of the dichotomy “humanity – nature”, “nature – human activity”,

“human power – negative consequences”, “fear – desire”, “good – value”, “nature – technologies”, “survival – catastrophes” outlined the problems of co-existence of man and the Earth in the conditions of a technological civilization, which is associated with the attraction of theoretical and practical achievements of biology, genetics, technical knowledge, natural sciences, social science, etc.

G. Jonas deals with the provisions that are not inherent in metaphysics and traditional ethics. He focuses on thinking about the future in the context of practical philosophy, where he emphasizes: humanity must live and be. He applies the principle of responsibility, which embodies the new worldview guidelines of a person at the beginning of the XXI century. Technique, as the philosopher believed, to one degree or another went beyond the permissible limits and requires restraint. Technological progress poses a threat to the existence of the Earth, its absolute existence, because nature is becoming more and more vulnerable: “The conquest of nature, aimed at the happiness of people, with its excessive successes, which extend to the nature of man itself, has turned into a challenge to human existence as such” [14]. The conceptual nature of G. Jonas’s research is aimed at substantiating the importance of humanity’s awareness of responsibility for their actions, which are ambivalent in nature.

We are talking about the need to rethink the relationship between man and the Earth in a situation where technologies are the main mediator of their co-existence. This allows to say that the main goal is to overcome both the safety in the use of technology and the absolute belief in the correctness and irrefutability of its use. Therefore, the task of modern man is not to exalt technology or, on the contrary, to underestimate the importance of technology for the present and future of humanity – it lies in responsibility. Therefore, ethics should be a model for collective responsibility for the future consequences of technologization.

The main task of G. Jonas considers control over the potential capabilities of a person and its activities. In proposing the principle of responsibility, he emphasizes two main aspects: the preservation of the Earth in its various modes and the preservation of human life. In this it is possible to see a new configuration of the co-existence of man and the Earth, where the ideas of philosophy, theology and science acquire a new sound. This approach has found wide resonance in Western philosophy. In connection with the ambivalence of actions, he offers “practical instructions” that embody the main idea: “Humanity has no right to destroy itself” [14]. Human actions should not jeopardize the future of humanity. In proposing the principle of responsibility, he emphasizes two main aspects: preserving the Earth in its various modes and preserving human life/being.

The concept of “environmental ethics” is being updated, because the basic principles of environmental law were recognized at the UN conference in Rio de Janeiro in June 1992, and was called the “Earth Summit”. The Declaration contains 27 principles, where, in the coordinates of sustainable development, the following range of problems is covered: “man/woman/indigenous population – responsibility of states and strengthening their cooperation – nature protection and ecosystem restoration – deepening scientific knowledge – openness and free access to information” [15].

The main question arises of limiting the invasion of human activity into the space of the Earth, conceptualizes the concept of “Ethics of the Earth”. We are talking about a new configuration of ethics as an attempt to take care of not only people, but also all living things that exist on Earth, because, sharing political, social, cultural and other views, a person does not cease to be a man of the Earth. A person is looking for ways to maintain, create, provide the necessary relationship with the Earth in order to ensure physical existence, during which the reproduction/formation of a person takes place. Human existence unfolds not only thanks to the geosphere, it depends on the lithosphere, hydrosphere, atmosphere, biosphere, however, a person ontologically corresponds to the Earth, therefore, must protect the mechanisms of the Earth’s self-development, protect it from comprehensive human control in a technological culture.

The study of the problem of the Ethics of the Earth has significant prospects in the scientific and humanitarian discourse of the beginning of the XXI century. In particular, the formation of the Ethics of the Earth makes rethink not only the relationship of a person with the social world in the plane of ethics, but also the relationship with the “Other”, which was the object of transformative activity. The definition of the Earth as an insurmountable component of human existence (M. Heidegger) in a situation of technological culture overcomes the absolutization of any monoparadigmatic approach and provides new opportunities for analyzing the phenomenon of the Earth in various fields of socio-humanitarian knowledge.

4. Conclusions

The definition of the technological culture of the late Modern era made it possible to determine the existing contradictions in the moral dimension of the existence of man and the Earth. It should be noted that in the context of the technological transformation of the Earth, the existing ethics as a monoparadigm of the Enlightenment does not correspond to the challenges of the beginning of the XXI century. Thus, the ethical dimension of the introduction of technology into the existence of the Earth is an indispensable component of modern scientific discourse. It is not only about the ethical dimension of technology, but also the importance of the formation of the Ethics of the Earth. This allows to conclude that a person determines its moral position relative to the Earth in the context of the technological transformation of the Earth's existence. It should be noted that the formation of the Ethics of the Earth determines a new promising direction in the development of philosophical anthropology. The application of the Ethics of the Earth is able to overcome the tension in the "man – nature/Earth" system, which is increasing exponentially since the moment of the "disenchantment" of the world by modern European science, due to the increase in technological impact. The approval of the Ethics of the Earth changes the configuration of human interactions with the outside world, which is associated with a rethinking of responsibility for the life of both people and non-people. Only by realizing this, a person will be able to break out of the trap of his own technological activity, it becomes absolutized in the paradigm of technological culture.

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